

Locus of Control as a Correlate of Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between locus of control and secondary school students' academic achievement in Imo State. Correlation research design was adopted for this study. Five research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were posed and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population for this study consisted of 8,463 Senior Secondary School (SS2) students. Research sample consisted of 860 (420 male and 440 female) students selected through multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument used for the study was Trice's Academic Locus of Control Scale (LOS). Results obtained from the study indicated that majority of the students in Imo state have external locus of control. The result also indicated that a good number of the students in Imo state have good achievement in English language and mathematics. Finally, the result revealed significant low positive relationships between secondary school students' locus of control and their academic achievement in English Language and Mathematics respectively. The study recommended, among others that Counsellors, teachers, parents and other stakeholders should focus more on changing students' locus of control from external to internal, so that students would be able to accept responsibility for their academic outcomes.

Keywords: Locus of Control, Academic Achievement, Students, Secondary school

Introduction

In Nigeria, particularly in Imo state, academic achievement is considered as a criterion to judge students' total potentialities and capabilities. Perhaps, this was the reason why Oguzie, Nwokolo, Mokwelu and Ezunu (2019) stressed that students' academic achievement occupies a vital position in the educational system as well as in the learning process. Hence, academic

achievement is very important for students, teachers, parents, governments and other stakeholders. This is why the government, teachers, psychologists, school counsellors, parents and examination bodies are greatly concerned with and are working very hard to unravel the mystery behind the poor academic achievement among students.

Reacting to the issue of poor academic achievement among secondary school students, Adeyemo (2007) emphasized that every stakeholder is concerned about how best to improve the academic achievement of students. This may be probably because educational attainment is highly fundamental to the realization of the scientific, technological, socio-economic and political development of any nation as well as the total empowerment and transformation of the citizens. Academic achievement is defined as the general performance of students in their offered subjects with respect to a specific standard called pass mark. Avoseh (2008) viewed it as how well an individual has done in a particular academic task. Steinmayr, Dinger and Spinath (2012) described academic achievement as the result of intellectual performance in schools; an education parameter which determines students' success in the school activities.

Academic achievement is a term usually employed to describe an individual's performance in subjects taught and tested in schools (Mkpae, & Obowu-Adutchay, 2017). It is the overall measured cognitive, affective and psychomotor achievement of a student with which they are judged academically fit or unfit (Okafor, Obi & Oguzie, 2018). More so, Oguzie, Nwokolo, Mokwelu and Ezunu (2019) viewed academic achievement as students' scholastic ability and attainment, which signifies the overall level of knowledge they have acquired in school, a subject, or a particular learning activity, process or situation. In the context of this study, academic achievement is taken to mean a symbol that indicates the level of knowledge/experience a student has acquired in a particular course of study and their ability to communicate this knowledge/experience in oral or in written form. It is the yardstick with which educational outcomes are measured.

Over the years, poor academic achievements in English Language and Mathematics among secondary school students have been on the increase. This is evident in the report on general performance of candidates in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE), presented by the Head of the National Council. For instance, in 2013, out of 298,971 candidates who sat for the examination, a total of 86,612 (29%) candidates obtained credits in five subjects and above including English Language and Mathematics while in 2014 out of 241,161 candidates who sat for the November/December West African Senior School Certificate Examination, only 72,522 (30.1%) scored five credits in English Language, Mathematics, Biology and any two other subjects (considered as the pass mark for the examination).

Studies have shown that several factors such as students' self esteem, self concept, self regulation, study behaviour, gender and socio-economic background influence students' academic achievement (Adeyemo, 2010; Okafor, Obi & Oguzie, 2018; Oguzie, Nwokolo, Mokwelu & Ezunu, 2019). Udoh (2012) maintained that academic achievement of students is a phenomenon that has educational, psychological and sociological connotation. This clearly signifies that students' academic achievement cannot be completely accounted for by only one or two variables but a number of them. Therefore, it is very pertinent to take full cognizance of the

multivariate nature of the issue of students' academic achievement and the need to explore other relevant factors such as locus of control that may influence it. In the light of this, the researchers determined the relationship that exists between students' locus of control and their academic achievement in secondary schools in Imo state.

Rotter (1966) laid a good foundation of the meaning of locus of control as a generalized belief of an individual about the underlying causes of events in his/her life. Locus of control refers to the types of attributions we make for our successes and/or failures in school tasks (Grantz, 2015). Individuals hold different beliefs about the things that control their destiny, and these beliefs give the kind of attitude people adopt towards an event in their lives (Oguzie, Ani, Obi & Onyegirim, 2018; Oguzie & Nwokolo 2019). Wood, Saylor and Cohen (2009) divided locus of control into two dimensions namely, internal and external locus of control. Students who have internal locus of control believe that their behaviours are guided by their personal decisions and efforts while those with external locus of control believe that their behaviours are guided by external circumstances. Sheikhi and Yousefzadeh (2011) were of the view that students with internal locus of control have better control of their behaviours and decisions and are more likely to take their studies serious and assume their efforts determine their success. Furthermore, research by Rana, Muammer and Zeynep (2011) showed that having an internal locus of control is related to higher academic achievement. However, in the context of this study, locus of control will be referred to as an individual's generalized expectations concerning where control over subsequent events resides. It represents an individuals' belief of who or what is responsible for what happens in the individual's life. Locus of control is a students' belief system regarding the causes of their academic experiences and the factors to which students attribute their success or failure in academic. Students' locus of control signifies whom or what they attribute the causes of their success and failure in school. For instance, if a student believes that his or her successes and failures are due to factors within their own control, such as effort or ability, then that student is said to have an internal locus of control. On the other hand, if a student believes that his or her academic successes and failures are due to factors beyond his or her own control, such as fate or luck, then that student is said to have an external locus of control. Students with internal locus of control spend more time in their studies so as to better retain the knowledge they have acquired, and this invariably rewards them with better scores and achievements in their academic pursuit. Since achievement has been identified to play an important role in the lives and activities of human beings (Oguzie, Oguzie, Nnadi, Mokwelu & Obi, 2019), the current researchers thus found it very necessary to investigate a salient variable that can influence academic achievement of secondary school students.

Moreover, the available literature has shown that studies seeking to address this issue in the Nigeria context particularly from the perspective of Imo State secondary schools are insufficient. This is a dearth in literature and a gap that needs to be filled. To this end, the present study focused on finding out the relationship that exists between locus of control and academic achievement of secondary school students in Imo state.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine locus of control as a correlate of secondary school students' academic achievements in Imo State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The locus of control scores of secondary school students in Imo state.
2. The achievement scores of secondary school students in English Language.
3. The achievement scores of secondary school students in Mathematics.
4. The type of relationship that exists between secondary school students' locus of control and their academic achievement in English Language.
5. The type of relationship that exists between secondary school students' locus of control and their academic achievement in Mathematics.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the locus of control scores of secondary school students?
2. What are the achievement scores of secondary school students in English Language?
3. What are the achievement scores of secondary school students in Mathematics?
4. What is the relationship between secondary school students' locus of control and their academic achievement in English Language?
5. What is the relationship between secondary school students' locus of control and their academic achievement in Mathematics?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between secondary school students' locus of control and their academic achievement in English language.
2. There is no significant relationship between secondary school students' locus of control and their academic achievement in Mathematics.

Method

This study adopted the correlation research design. According to Nworgu (2015), this type of study seeks to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables. Usually such studies indicate the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables. Egereonu (2011) observed that the result is expressed in correlation coefficients, that is, the degree of relationship is expressed in numerical forms, between -1.00 to +1.00. The population of the study comprised of 8,463 students (Source: Imo State Secondary Education Management Board, IMSEMB, 2017). This consisted of all the senior secondary two (SS 2) students from all the public secondary schools in Imo State, under the management of IMSEMB. The sample size for the study consisted of 860 (420 males and 440 females) SS2 students drawn from the entire population through multi-stage sampling.

The instrument was used for data collection the Trice's Academic Locus of Control Scale (LOS) developed by Asthon Trice in 1985. This instrument consisted of 28 'True' or 'False' items used to measure Locus of Control. The Trice's academic Locus of Control Scale (LOS) was found to be internally consistent (coefficient alpha = .70), and test-retest reliability coefficient was $r = .92$ (Trice, 1985). The convergent validity was supported via strong correlations with Rotter's I-E

Scale ($r = .77$). Lease (2010) recommended the use of LOS as an appropriate instrument for measuring students' locus of control. The instrument used to collect data for the students' academic achievement in English language and Mathematics was the Teachers' Grade Books/Score Inventory. This is a record book where students' scores are recorded by their teachers. This was gotten from the English and mathematics teachers in the schools used in the study. Hence, the students' scores in the two compulsory school subjects in their last central promotion examinations were used to represent their academic achievement scores (Source: Imo State Secondary Education Management Board, IMSEMB, 2016).

The researchers administered copies of the instruments through direct delivery method. In each school, a letter of introduction was presented to the school principal for approval. Then the researchers with the help of five research assistants who were duly briefed distributed copies of the instruments to the respondents (students) and also retrieved the completed copies of the instruments for scoring and analysis. Five research assistants participated in this study. The research assistants were well informed about the purpose of the study and the methods used. More so, the research assistants were properly intimated about the method of administration and collection of the instruments for data collection and better ways of approaching the respondents (students). Finally, the research assistants were urged to call the researcher's attention if they encounter any challenge during the administration and collection of the instruments. The completed instruments for this study were scored following the scoring instruction. All data to be collected for this study were organised in tables and analysed. Summated scores descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used to analyse the data collected for the study.

Results

Table 1: Range of mean scores on students' locus of control

Range of scores	N	%	Remarks
28 – 55	338	39.3	Internal locus of control
56 – 112	522	60.7	External locus of control

Table 1 shows that 522(60.7%) of the students with the scores ranging from 56 to 112 have external locus of control, while 338(39.3%) of the students who scored between 28 and 55 have internal locus of control.

Table 2: Range of achievement mean scores of students in English language

Range of scores	N	%	Remarks
0 – 49	90	10.5	Poor achievement
50 – 69	290	33.7	Average achievement
70 – 100	480	55.8	Good achievement

Table 2 indicates that 480(55.8%) of the students with the scores ranging from 70 to 100 have good achievement in English language, while 290(33.7%) students who scored between 50 and 69 have average achievement where 90(10.5%) of the students have poor achievement in English language.

Table 3: Range of achievement mean scores of students in Mathematics

Range of scores	N	%	Remarks
0 – 49	63	7.4	Poor achievement
50 – 69	229	26.6	Average achievement
70 – 100	568	66.0	Good achievement

Table 3 reveals that 568(66.0%) of the students with the scores ranging from 70 to 100 have good achievement in mathematics, while 229(26.6%) students who scored between 50 and 69 have average achievement where 63(7.4%) of the students have poor achievement in mathematics.

Table 4: Pearson r on students' locus of control and their achievement scores in English language

Source of Variation	N	Locus of Control r	Achievements r	Remark
Locus of control	860	1.00	0.22	Low Positive Relationship
Achievements	860	0.22	1.00	

In table 4, it was observed that there is low positive relationship of 0.22 existing between the students' locus of control and their achievements in English language in secondary schools.

Table 5: Pearson r on students' locus of control and their achievement scores in Mathematics

Source of Variation	N	Locus of control r	Achievements r	Remark
Locus of control	860	1.00	0.38	Low Positive Relationship
Achievements	860	0.38	1.00	

Table 5 shows that, there is low positive relationship of 0.38 existing between the students' locus of control and their achievements in Mathematics in secondary schools.

Table 6: significance of Pearson r on the students' locus of control and their achievements in English language using probability table of r

N	cal. r	df	pvalue	Cal.pvalue	Remark
860	0.22	858	0.05	0.00	S

S = Significant

Table 6 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance and 858df, the calculated r0.22 has pvalue 0.00 which is less than critical pvalue 0.05. Therefore the first null hypothesis is rejected. The type of relationship existing between the students' locus of control and their achievements in English language in secondary schools is significant.

Table 7: significance of Pearson r on the students' locus of control and their achievements in mathematics using probability table of r

N	cal. r	df	pvalue	Cal.pvalue	Remark
860	0.38	858	0.05	0.00	S

S = Significant

In table 7, it was observed that at 0.05 level of significance and 858df, the calculated r0.38 has pvalue 0.00 which is less than critical pvalue 0.05. Therefore the second null hypothesis is rejected. The type of relationship existing between the students' locus of control and their achievements in mathematics in secondary schools is significant.

Discussion

The results of this study revealed that majority of secondary school students (60.7%) in Imo state have external locus of control. This may have resulted from the various perfidious means of passing examinations available in the present education system. Many students may have developed the idea that whatsoever grade they obtain in their examination is determined by their teachers or examiners and not by their own performance. This finding is consistent with the reports from previous researchers (Nwankwo, Balogun, Chukwudi & Ibeme, 2012; Kalantarkousheh, Mahogheghi & Hossieni, 2013) that majority of secondary school students have external locus of control. However, this finding goes contrary with (Majzub, Tallaq, Bataineh & Rahman, 2009) who reported that majority of secondary school students have internal locus of control. The reason for the finding of this study contradicting the report of Majzub and his group may be as a result of difference in location. Maybe, the cultural background in Majzub's area is such that facilitates self belief. Since majority of the students have external locus of control, it could possibly indicate that majority of students in Imo state attribute their success and failures to external factors. Sheikhi and Yousefzadeh (2011) emphasized that students with external locus of control have lesser control over their behaviours and decisions, and are less likely to take their studies serious.

Another finding showed that a good number of students (55.8%) in Imo state have good level of academic achievement English Language. The result also indicated that a good number of students (60.0%) in Imo state have good level of academic achievement in Mathematics. This result shows that despite the discouraging effect of the economic situation of the country and the high rate of unemployment among Imo graduates, secondary school students in Imo state still work hard to excel in their academic pursuit. The above finding is in consonance with the report of previous researchers (Garikai, 2010; Bahogo, 2011; Okafor, Obi & Oguzie, 2018) who found that many students have high academic achievement. However, the finding contradicts the finding by (Obi, 2016) who reported that majority of secondary school students have low academic achievement.

It is important to note, that secondary school students' academic achievement is clearly linked to their subsequent social, economic and health outcome (Heckman, 2006). Also, Staffolani and Bratti (2012) observed that students' previous educational outcome are the most important indicators of their future achievement. This signifies that the higher the previous academic achievement, the better the students' academic achievement. Since, a good number of the students have high academic achievement, it may therefore be right to assume that if students are provided with more serene teaching and learning atmosphere, they will be encouraged to put more effort toward achieving academic excellence, and this will further encourage better academic achievements in future.

The result of the study also revealed that the students' locus of control has low positive significant relationship with their academic achievement in both English Language and Mathematics. This finding is consistent with the outcome of many previous research works (Anakwe, 2008; Barzega, 2011; Biggs, 2007; Nejati, Abedi, Agbaci & Mohammadi, 2012; Shepherd, Owen, Fitch & Marsall, 2006; Talla, 2007) which reported that students' locus of control

significantly correlated with their academic achievement. Students with good locus of control spend more time in their studies so as to better retain the knowledge they have acquired, and this invariably rewards them with better grades and achievements with more interest in their studies and this could be a possible reason for the above finding. Supporting this, Sheikhi and Yousefzadeh (2011) noted that students with better locus of control have better control of their behaviours and decisions and are more likely to take their studies serious and assume their efforts determine their academic successes. However, this finding contradicts some other previous researchers who reported that locus of control had no relationship with students' academic achievement (Jeffreys, 2008; Reynolds & Weigand, 2010; Dinçyürek, Güneşli & Çallar, 2012). It is also very important that the positive relationship between students' locus of control and their academic achievement found in this study is low. While the results of previous researchers showed that academic achievement had high positive relationships with other variables such as self-esteem and study behaviour (Okafor, Obi & Oguzie, 2018; Oguzie, Nwokolo, Mokwelu & Ezunu, 2019). This could be an indication that the main causes of poor academic achievement among students are variables like self-esteem and study behaviour, and not necessarily the students' locus of control.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers concluded that majority of the students in Imo state have external locus of control. A good number of the students in Imo state have good achievement in English language and mathematics. Again, there is a significant low positive relationship between secondary school students' locus of control and their academic achievement in English language and Mathematics respectively.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Counsellors, teachers, parents and other stakeholders should focus more on changing students' locus of control from external to internal, so that students would be able to accept responsibility for their academic outcomes.
2. Parents, government and other stakeholders should come up with reinforcing packages in form of incentives, scholarships, and promotions so as to encourage students to maintain good academic achievement and strive to achieve better in future.
3. Since there is low positive relationship between students' locus of control and their academic achievement, Guidance Counsellors should therefore pay more attention to other factors such as self-esteem, study behaviour, among others when fighting the problem of poor academic achievement among secondary school students.
4. Students should be given leadership roles so as to create a sense of belonging among them, thereby enabling them to take responsibilities of their actions in the schools. This will also enable them to cultivate and maintain the belief that their level of effort determines their level of achievements in school.

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